

Against Absolutism: Towards a New Filipino Aristocracy

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Many Filipinos uphold the idea of a strong, centralized, and autocratic state as the salvation of a long suffering nation from decades of incompetence and corruption under the Fifth Republic. This sentiment is not lost among even traditional Catholics, many of whom take either monarchist or clerical-fascist ideological strides. The logic behind this is that the moral order requires a strong, empowered, State to be its chief protector and upholder. What many fail to realize, however, is that absolutist systems (big government) are per se contrary to Catholic Social Teaching and the common good, inasmuch as it violates the principles of subsidiarity and consists of the centralization of power. Furthermore, any appeal to a Catholic absolutism (a contradiction in terms) would, in the long run, work against the Catholic interest. But in order to understand why this would be the case, we would need to look into what absolutism *does*.

The Absolutist Revolution and its Consequences

At first glance, absolutism goes hand-in-hand with the Divine right of kings. But Bertrand de Jouvenel rightfully noted that the idea of “Divine right” actually put limits on the power of the monarch, for he was constrained by God’s will in addition to custom (B. de Jouvenel, *On Power*, p. 30). He instead proposes that it was the emancipation of the monarch’s power from the restraints of the Church that led to the rise of absolutism, ironically under the banner of popular sovereignty (pp. 31-35).² The King also had to contend with the nobility, for it served to check monarchical power (Jouvenel, *On Power*, p. 188).³ The King of France, however, found that he could undermine the aristocracy by empowering those of inferior social rank in his court, thus making a loyal class of people raised from nothing by his grace (181).⁴ Hence, appeals to the people against the aristocracy proved to work in the sovereign’s favor.

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² The idea that the people must have a say in politics is not alien to the teachings of the Catholic Church (ibid., pp. 31-32; Pontifical Council for Justice and Peace, *Compendium of the Social Doctrine of the Church*, 395). The problem, however, was that the Jesuit concept “was soon distorted, as we shall see, in such a way that it served to justify absolutism” by simply removing the principle that God is the “author of power”, thus reformulating it so that “Power belongs to society in full fee simple and is then conferred by it alone on its rulers” (p. 33).

³ *Vide* L.A. de Bonald, *Theorie du pouvoir politique et religieux dans la société civile*, 3 vols., tome III, pp. 255-256.

⁴ As Tocqueville mentions in *Democracy in America* (2 vols): “In France the kings have always been the most active and the most constant of levellers” (vol.1, introductory chapter).

Similar trends can be observed in the Philippines, in which Duterte’s propaganda campaign appealed to populist narratives against political dynasties, oligarchs, and the like. As Fellglow Keep writes, “These narratives of power point to the former as the real brokers, and the latter as helpless victims in a failing state.”⁵ However, he posits rather that in reality, dynasties etc. “do the national government's dirty work, and in exchange, they get to keep some power”, though the government can easily check their power by force of military or police (ibid). As it is in the nature of Power to grow and expand (Jouvenel, *On Power*, pp. 126-128), it must always “invoke the public interest ... It looks as though the advance of the state is a means to the advance of the individual” (p. 129-130). One such way is to channel the frustrations of ordinary people against local elites (p. 130).

Absolutism and Nationalism

The rise of absolutism was also concomitant with nationalism. According to Jouvenel, as the centralized King began to personify the nation, the nation began to take on its own personification following the 1789 Revolution: “It was not that the throne was overthrown, but that the whole, the nation-person, mounted it. Its life was as that of the king it succeeded, but it had one great advantage over him: for subjects are, in regard to a king—who is seen to be a person different from themselves—naturally careful to secure their rights. Whereas the nation is not a person different: it is the subject himself, and yet it is more than he—it is a hypostatized We” (pp. 47-48). This new, revolutionary, idea of “nation” with all its emotive power allowed for Power to maintain a stronger hold over the population. This new concept of society, which Jouvenel calls “Realist”, carries over its Rousseauian implications to the fore, for a personalized society would now possess a general will (pp. 9-11).

The implications of this are such that now, the general will is represented only by those who know what they truly, really, want (49-50). And by appealing to this general will “From being but *one* interest in society, an eminent and essential one certainly,” Power “became *the* interest of society” (254). Duterte appealed to nationalism in order to win over the population, and thus became its representative (Teehankee, *Journal of Current Southeast Asian Affairs* 35:3). His regime was marked by the increase of police power (the war on drugs) and an increase in military power (Marawi, war against communists). As written by Segundo Romero, Jr., “There has been a re-centralization of power from local to the national government, as local governments now implement initiatives emanating from Malacañang, such as the anti-drug campaign, implementation of curfew” (*HBS Southeast Asia*, 26 September 2016).

⁵ Fellglow Keep, “Why Are Philippine Oligarchs and Dynasties Used as Boogeymen?” *Pillar of Liberty*, 20 September 2022.

Absolutism in Elite Theory

Absolutism also came with the institutional displacement of the aristocratic elite in favor of capitalists, the bourgeoisie (Jouvenel, *Du pouvoir*, p. 185) who were often considered to be middle class or nouveau riche. In the case of the Philippines, Duterte's campaign appealed to the middle class and nouveau riche, being "the angry protest of the wealthy, newly rich, well off, and the modestly successful new middle class..." (Teehankee, *Journal of Current Southeast Asian Affairs* 35:3, p. 72). He lampooned old aristocratic institutions such as the Catholic Church and genteel manners (Teehankee, *Journal of Current Southeast Asian Affairs* 35:3, p. 73).⁶ A similar thing happened with Ferdinand E. Marcos, whose attempts to undermine the oligarchy gave rise to a new elite of cronies and military generals.⁷

This conflict is most relevant in terms of the dominant culture in a given society, inasmuch as "ruling classes do not justify their power exclusively by de facto possession of it, but try to find a moral and legal basis for it, representing it as the logical and necessary consequence of doctrines and beliefs that are generally recognized and accepted."⁸ In the Philippines, the local and outgoing *principalia* contrasted themselves with the new Americanized elite by appealing to their possession of *delicadeza* (Roces, *Fashion Theory* 17:3, 357-358). Even to this day, "new money" elites often despise their "old money" counterparts for riding on the coattails of their ancestors, while the latter would view the former as arrogant, uncultured philistines.

Institutional Subversion

With this background in mind, it becomes clear why the absolutist question must be spoken of in terms of elites, or what Pareto calls "the strongest, the most energetic, and most capable—for good as well as evil" (V. Pareto, *The Rise and Fall of the Elites*, p. 36). They are "a class of the people who have the highest indices in their branch of activity..." (V. Pareto, *The Mind and Society*, III, p. 1423). However, Pareto continues, "due to an important physiological law, elites do not last. Hence—the history of man is the history of the continuous replacement of certain elites: as one ascends, another declines" (*The Rise and Fall of the Elites*, p. 36). Thus, there is always room for elite conflict. In the eighteenth to nineteenth centuries, the power center appealed to the bourgeois interest (Jouvenel, *Du pouvoir*, p. 185). But soon enough, the State turned on its erstwhile allies, and began to encroach on their affairs (pp. 169-170).

Hence, Jouvenel predicted an alliance between the State and the "syndicate," but also noted that if the State would not turn on its new ally, "...it will be the syndicalist feudalisms, and

⁶ Duterte himself comes from a very old and genteel family. G.S. Bagares, "'Kanto boy'? Duterte is so 'de buena familia' ('sa totoo lang')," 29 May 2016 *Inquirer Lifestyle*.

⁷ M. Roces, "Dress, Status, and Identity in the Philippines: Pineapple Fiber Cloth and Ilustrado Fashion" (2013 *Fashion Theory* 17:3, p. 362).

⁸ G. Mosca, *The Ruling Class: Elementi di Scienza Politica*, 1965 McGraw-Hill with H. Khan, translator and A. Livingston, editor, p. 70.

not itself, which will exercise the vast powers committed to it by individuals. And the state will then be the "public thing" of the syndicalist feudalisms" (pp. 171-172). After all, it is in the interests of corporate expansion to subvert the bourgeois (Francis, *Samuel Francis*, pp. 10-24). This interest is also shared by the owners of the large corporations, for they are "already wealthy and are less concerned with the dividend yield than with the increase in or stability of the value of their stock", the latter of which corporate growth offers (p. 13). Hence for all intents and purposes they shall be classified as managerial elites (pp. 90-98).

The Clash of Civilizations

The clash between such elite interests, however, has culture as its battleground. As James Burnham notes, "All organized societies are cemented together...also by accepted ways of feeling and thinking and talking and looking at the world, by ideologies" (*The Managerial Revolution*, p. 175). Hence, the conflict between the incumbent managerial elite and the outgoing bourgeois manifests itself in the clash of civilizations. As Samuel Francis notes, "The interests of the managerial elite lie in the growth and expansion not only of the mass corporation but also of the mass state and mass society, the scope of mass organizations in general, and the subversion of bourgeois and prescriptive institutions that constrain the enlargement and functioning of mass organizations" (p. 15).

This interest specifically consisted in "destroying the individualism and diversity of the bourgeois order through its collective discipline and homogenizing processes" and subverting "the bourgeois work ethic and its derivative values through its promotion of mass hedonism and consumption" (p. 20). This subversion has a name, "managerial humanism": the ideological sum of "scientism, utopianism, hedonism, and cosmopolitanism" which justifies corporate expansion (p. 143). For cosmopolitanism encouraged man "to reject national, class, racial, and regional identities" which were crucial to bourgeois society (p. 156), as scientism and environmentalism relativized and reduced man and culture to materialistic and environmental considerations (p. 143, pp. 152-157), and hedonism encouraged deviance from bourgeois culture (pp. 155-157).

Elite Dynamics in the Philippines

However, in order to understand the implications of these dynamics in Philippine culture and society, we must understand the nature of the Filipino aristocracy. Unlike France which had a social stratification system based, in part, on the possession of noble rank and title, Philippine culture has been characterized more by social mobility (F. Lynch, "Social Acceptance Reconsidered," pp. 1-63), thus making it so that a rich commoner family could one day become *de buena familia*.⁹ Furthermore, the native *mestizo* aristocracy closed ranks with some Chinese

⁹ This is very similar to the concept of the gentleman (Cf. C. Berberich, *The Idea of the English Gentleman in Twentieth-Century Literature*, p. 33; R. Gilmour, *The Idea of the Gentleman in the Victorian Novel*, pp. 4-7; P. Mason, *The English Gentleman*, p. 13; A. de Tocqueville, *The Old Regime and the Revolution*, p. 108). Tocqueville claims that in the United States, this term is "indiscriminately applied to all classes" (*The Old Regime and the*

merchant families: “Since a measure of political clout and money invariably attract each other, the two classes fused” (Mulder, 2013 *Journal of Current Southeast Asian Affairs* 31:1, p. 70). This is a classic example of the interaction between what Mosca called in *The Ruling Class* the “democratic” i.e. and “aristocratic” tendencies of elites (p. 419).¹⁰ Indeed, Robert Michels notes that Pareto’s theory of elite conflict is not as clear cut as presented, as old elites often assimilate the new into their ranks (R. Michels, *Political Parties*, p. 225).

We can consider with ease how noble or at least respectable families have made their way to the top of managerial corporations: House Tuason, House Zobel de Ayala, etc. Even more families have taken possession of State institutions, such as the Madrigal and Romualdez clans. This elite, Mulder complains, generally looks out for its own interests and not the public good (*opere citato*, 70-71). Thus, appeals against these elites become part and parcel of populism, a main tactic of state centralization as mentioned before. In acting against the oligarchy, Ferdinand Marcos created “a new rich that included his cronies and the military.”¹¹ However, the dispossessed elite families returned with a vengeance and ousted him in the 1986 Revolution.¹² Another symbolic push against the oligarchy, as mentioned before, was that of the Duterte campaign (Teehankee, *Journal of Current Southeast Asian Affairs*, 35:3, p. 72).

Towards a New Filipino Aristocracy

Knowing that it is in the societal interest of the managerial corporation to subvert old aristocratic and bourgeois institutions, and that the particular way in which this is done is contrary to the Catholic ethic, it behooves the Catholic conscience to think of effective ways in which this trend may be countered. The fact of the matter is, however, that the Philippine State currently favors big corporations over small businesses or provincial landowners. State institutions are furthermore complicit in the rise of cosmopolitan cultural relativism among the social consciousness, which is harmful to Catholic culture as a whole. As it maintains control over academic institutions (thus gatekeeping elite formation in the Philippines), it has guaranteed that the next generation of literati are inculcated with some form of woke ideology while media corporations disseminate their propaganda to the educated public.

As previously mentioned, many members of the landowning and bourgeois elite have adapted to the managerial framework, thus assimilating themselves into the ruling class. This should not be an occasion of shock, as plenty of landed families have had no scruples in entering

Revolution, p. 108). However, E. Digby Baltzell writes in *Philadelphia Gentleman* that some measure of social stratification developed revolving around membership in the social clubs (p. 340). The same term, *gentleman*, has been used to denote members of the bourgeoisie who have adopted aristocratic customs (I. Buruma, *Voltaire’s Coconuts*, 2000 Phoenix, p. 9).

¹⁰ Cf. Francis, *Leviathan and its Enemies*, p. 419.

¹¹ M. Roces, “Dress, Status, and Identity in the Philippines: Pineapple Fiber Cloth and Ilustrado Fashion” (2013 *Fashion Theory* 17:3, p. 362).

¹² Shay Cullen, “The Success and Failure of the EDSA Revolution,” 26 February 2016 PREDA Foundation.

the world of commerce.¹³ However, this means that plenty of *de buena familia* elites have adopted the managerial ideology as their own. With it comes a rejection of traditions and other institutions proper to the aristocratic class in favor of a homogeneous culture facilitated by the Internet. Politically, “wokism” is taking root in private and international schools (which, as a rule, are part of the elite formation process) as the alienation of elites from the rest of Philippine society is exploited in order to motivate young, impressionable elites into subverting their own institutions.

The Formation and Constitution of the New Aristocracy

What, therefore, must be done? The first thing is that we must acknowledge that in order to win the clash of civilizations in favor of Catholic values, politically oriented Catholics and conservatives must find a way to consolidate family interests, i.e. those of provincial landed families and local business families, both victims of the expansion of the managerial corporations and the State apparatus. It must be noted, though, that while the bourgeois is generally antithetical to nobility, it *does* happen that a bourgeois family, on account of its gradual refinement in customs or “family traditions” and intergenerational commitment to the common good, is either assimilated into the aristocratic class or forms a new, analogous, aristocracy, thus joining the ranks of the traditional elite (P.C. de Oliveira, *Nobility and Analogous Traditional Elites*). Oliveria also includes among the elite professors, diplomats, commissioned officers, etc.

However, the expansionist State controls virtually all avenues for gainful employment, thus making it difficult to organize a sustainable counter-elite. This includes the State’s grip on academia and research, business registration and positive laws, etc. Yet a counter-elite can organize, consolidate and protect one another’s business interests through mutual exchange and cooperation.¹⁴ They may also form alternate means of education beyond the reach of the bureaucracy, particularly in local Catholic churches.¹⁵ For a counter-elite must possess a coherent cultural framework and worldview, passed down by the family and adjunct institutions.¹⁶ It is also important for counter-elites to win over sympathetic individuals from ruling institutions, though this may require on their part a sacrifice of economic or societal gain in favor of the common good.

¹³ According to E. Digby Baltzell, the American gentleman (unlike his English counterpart) had no qualms about conducting business or engaging himself in hard work. (*Philadelphia Gentlemen*, p. 57).

¹⁴ Here I am not specifically referring to the petit-bourgeois MSME or the yeoman family farm. I am referring to the rural landlord and the moderately established business, the *elite*.

¹⁵ For although the Catholic Church has officially adapted to managerial capitalism, it must be noted that “church life belongs in reality to the parish and its local traditions” (Mulder, *Journal of Current Southeast Asian Affairs*, 35:3, p. 72).

¹⁶ Cf. John Paul II, “Address of His Holiness John Paul II to the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization,” 1980 *UNESCO Courier* 33:6, pp. 12-14.

The Future of the Philippine Aristocracy

The Philippine aristocracy has gone a long way from its roots in the landowning provincial families of the colonial period. Today, the vast majority of them have gone into business, and a small minority of them have become owners and executives of big corporations. Although the adaptability of the Philippine elite has guaranteed their financial security, it has come at the cost of the local life and traditions, the sum of which is the soul of the nation, the common good: for in order to protect its economic interests, the “grande bourgeoisie” has become an “appendage to the managerial elite” (p. 94). This does not mean that the Filipino elite, in adapting to corporatism, have willingly abandoned their values, but rather, their values are no longer congruent with their economic interest (pp. 93-94).

Now, we can observe a growing trend of adherence to “woke” or progressive ideologies among young elites, facilitated in a large part by the international school system, along with the underlying economic interest of the big corporation to “undermine, discredit, or subsume the institutions, values, and structures of the bourgeois order that constrain the pursuit of managerial interest” (Francis, *Leviathan and its Enemies*, p. 92). Hence, it is important to secure the economic autonomy and sustainability of any counter-elite (the New Aristocracy), so that their cultural interests shall not run directly against their economic ones. The formation of this alternate authority, this counter-elite, is *the* only way in which the ruling power’s expansionism may be kept in check, and outgoing elite groups may avoid being lost to the annals of history, which is, as Pareto says, “a graveyard of aristocracies” (*The Mind and Society*, III, p. 1430).

Author Note

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